

USE OF RESOLE SEPIOLITE-PHOSPHATE NANOCOMPOSITE FOR BUILDING FACADES

L. Soufeiani^{1*}, K. Nguyen², and G. Foliente¹

¹ Department of Infrastructure Engineering, The University of Melbourne, Melbourne, Australia

² School of Engineering, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia

Corresponding author (soufeiani.leila@gmail.com)

Keywords: Phenolic resin, Sepiolite-phosphate, Nanocomposite

ABSTRACT

COMBUSTIBILITY OF CLADDING MATERIALS IN THE FAÇADE SYSTEM IS THE MAIN ISSUE IN THE PREFABRICATED BUILDING ENVELOPES AS COMBUSTIBLE MATERIALS SPREAD THE FIRE RAPIDLY. INVESTIGATION OF NEW NANOCOMPOSITE MATERIAL TO BE REPLACED THE EXISTING COMBUSTIBLE CLADDING'S MATERIAL IS THE PURPOSE OF THE CURRENT STUDY. SEPIOLITE-PHOSPHATE (SEPP) HAS BEEN MADE AND DIFFERENT CONTENTS OF IT (3%, 5%, AND 10%) SYNTHESIZED WITH RESOLE PHENOLIC RESIN IN ORDER TO STUDY THE DISPERSION OF THE SEPP NANOPOWDERS IN THE PHENOLIC RESIN NANOCOMPOSITE. HELIUM ION MICROSCOPE (HIM) AND SCANNING ELECTRON MICROSCOPE (SEM) SHOWED THAT THE SEPP HAS BEEN MADE SUCCESSFULLY AND THE SEPP 3% HAD A BETTER DISPERSION IN THE PHENOLIC NANOCOMPOSITE.

1 INTRODUCTION

Building facades have the greatest level of failure as a building element [1, 2]. Recent catastrophic events with façade fires such as the Grenfell Tower fire (UK, 2017) and the Lacrosse Building fire (AU, 2014) have raised the awareness of fire safety in building facades and the increasing need for innovative façade materials which meet both structural and fire safety requirements [3, 4]. For this purpose, Nanocomposite materials are ideal due to their superior properties [5-7].

Among thermosetting resins which are used industrially, phenol-formaldehyde resins are mainly used due to their extensive application in wood adhesives, laminates, coatings, moldings, thermal insulation materials, and composites [8, 9]. Phenolic nanocomposite has a three dimensional (3D) molecular structure even before curing. Owing to the difficulties in synthesizing phenolic composite, not much research has been carried out [9-11]. Due to its high thermal stability with good smoke and fire resistance, phenolic resins (PRs) are attractive in structural applications at high temperatures [12]. Among existing nanomaterials, Sepiolite, $(Mg_8Si_{12}O_{30}(OH)_4(H_2O)_4 \cdot 8H_2O)$ which is a nanoclay fiber and has a large specific surface area (about $320 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$) [13] has been used in nanocomposites because of its needle-like structure, high surface area, and good ability of dispersion [14-16]. Palacios et al. [17] made Sepiolite-phosphate (SepP) with direct synthesis of aluminum phosphate on sepiolite nanofibers. They used sepiolite as a support to control the agglomeration and size of phosphate nanoparticles (halogen-free flame retardant) [17], and developed a new three-dimensional rigid supported phosphate structure during the thermal treatment. They concluded that the SepP has the potential to be used as a flame retardant [17].

Due to outstanding properties of phenolic resin and SepP's 3D structure at high temperatures, the authors propose resole/SepP nanocomposite as a prospective alternative for building facades cladding owing to the above mentioned advantages. Resole/SepP nanocomposite will be used in the glass fiber reinforced polymer nanocomposite for façade application.

In this study, SepP has been made with the precipitation synthesis method [17] to examine its characteristics and dispersion in the phenolic resin for flame retardant applications. In order to evaluate the morphology of the SepP, Helium Ion Microscopy (HIM) has been conducted due to its better resolution at high magnification over SEM. Then, different contents of SepP (3wt%, 5wt%, and 10wt%) in the phenolic resin were used to produce resole-SepP nanocomposite. After curing process, Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) has been carried to determine the dispersion of SepP in the phenolic resin, and its morphological characterization.

2 Materials and Preparation

2.1 Materials

Sepiolite powders (>95%, Pangel S9) were supplied from TOLSA S.A. Aluminum hydroxide, Hydrochloric acid 37%, Ortho-phosphoric acid 85%, and Ammonia solution 28-30% were purchased from MERCK. Phenolic resin and catalyst were purchased from Hexion Pty Ltd.

2.2 Experimental details

To obtain the 6% sepiolite, 6gr of sepiolite powder was dispersed in deionized water under high shear mixing for 5 minutes. Then HCl solution was added to adjust the pH around 2 under stirring. In addition, 2.33gr of $Al(OH)_3$ was dissolved in the aqueous solution of 17.33 gr of H_3PO_4 (Al/P:1/3 molar ratio), and stirred at room temperature to obtain a uniform solution. Then, this uniform solution was added to the initial sepiolite dispersion, and stirring was continued for 30 minutes. Thereafter, a NH_4OH solution was added dropwise to the solution until pH of 4.8 to produce the phosphate precipitation. Then, synthesized powders were filtered under vacuum, washed with deionized water,

and dried at 80°C for several hours. The final product is SepP nanopowders. Then morphological characterization has been conducted with Helium Ion Microscope (HIM- Zeiss Orion NanoFab).

In the next step, SepP with different contents by phenolic resin (PR) weight (3wt%, 5wt%, and 10wt%) was added to the PR with 5 minutes stirring at temperature 80 °C followed by 10 minutes sonication in the same temperature. Then, 5% catalyst was added to the SepP-PR and stirred for 2 minutes under room temperature to mix and turn the color of the solution to a lighter color. Thereafter, putting the sample in the oven for one hour at 80 °C. The phenol with viscosity 180-270 cPs, PH: 7-8, and water content 14-16%, and a catalyst with viscosity 150-350 cP and water content 20-28% was used in this study. Then, the PR structure was observed with scanning electron microscope (SEM-FEI Hitachi) in order to study the characterization of the nanocomposite. Table 1 shows composition of samples.

Table 1: Composition of samples

No	SepP	Phenolic resin	Catalyst
1	-	100%	5%
2	3%	100%	5%
3	5%	100%	5%
4	10%	100%	5%

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Morphological characterization of the sepiolite-phosphate (SepP) composites

In order to observe the dispersion state of the phosphate on the sepiolite fibers, Helium Ion Microscop (HIM- Zeiss Orion NanoFab) characterization was carried out on the SepP composite. Figure 1 shows HIM micrograph of SepP composite.

Figure 1: Micrograph of SepP composite: Uniform distribution of phosphate nanoparticles on the surface of sepiolite fibers. Fibers are fully covered by phosphate nanoparticles

From Figure 1, it can be seen that the phosphate particles covered the sepiolite fibers surface and distributed uniformly. The figure shows the typical geometry of sepiolite fibers which are 15-50 nm in diameter, and phosphate nanoparticles which are 40-80 nanometers. The micrograph displays a uniform distribution of phosphate on the sepiolite fibers surface.

3.2 Morphological characterization of SepP phenolic nanocomposite

SEM analysis was conducted to understand the phenolic resin structure and distribution of SepP nanoparticles in polymeric phenolic resin matrix. As seen in Figure 2, there are microvoids on the phenolic resin surface with diameter of less than 5 micrometers with an average diameter of 3.85 micrometers. The microvoid measurements are shown in Table 2.

Figure 2: Phenolic resin structure: (a) microvoids. (b) microvoids diameter measurements which are less than 5 micrometers

Table 2: Phenolic resin microvoids diameters

Voids	Label	Area	Diameter (μm)
1		0.624	4.055
2		0.713	4.578
3		0.401	2.481
4		0.757	4.975
5		0.713	4.594
6		0.557	3.582
7		0.668	4.254
8		0.668	4.383
9		0.579	3.669
10		0.557	3.632
11		0.49	3.147
12		0.535	3.389
13		0.646	4.184
14		0.468	3.011
	Mean	0.598	3.852

The emergence of microvoids is due to the release of by-product water molecules in the phenolic resin during polymerization. Water vapor bubbles getting trapped in the sample during curing and form macro and microvoids [18]. To reduce the number of defects and eliminate volatiles in the phenolic resin, an accurate temperature control and gradual heating is needed [19]. However, this type of porosity may decrease the structural strength. This may not be critical in the present study because the proposed nanocomposite will be used as a fire-resistant cladding material which is not load bearing.

Figure 3: (a) PR structure. (b) SepP (3%)-PR nanocomposite. (c) SepP(5%)-PR nanocomposite. (d) SepP(10%)-PR nanocomposite

Figure 3 (a) shows the micrograph of phenolic resin and Figure 3 (b, c, and d) shows different contents of SepP nanopowders in the phenolic resin structure. It can be seen that the SepP nanopowders are not dispersed uniformly and agglomeration can be seen mostly for SepP5% and 10%. Further investigation on SepP agglomeration in the phenolic resin with HIM will be conducted and presented in the conference.

4. Conclusion

The investigation of SepP in the phenolic resin has been carried out for the first time in this research. HIM showed that the SepP nanopowders formed effectively and phosphate nanoparticles uniformly covered the surface of sepiolite fibers. SEM micrograph of phenolic resin showed its porous structure due to evaporation of the water. Different contents of SepP in the phenolic resin have been investigated and SEM micrograph showed that 3% of SepP had a better dispersion in the nanocomposite. The next step will be high shear mixing of resole-SepP nanocomposite to prevent

agglomeration and make a uniform dispersion. The proposed phenolic nanocomposite will be used with 3D glass fibers to make a 3DGFRC nanocomposite for façade application.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was conducted with the financial support of the CRC-Project on Advanced Manufacturing of High Performance Building Envelope Systems (CRC-P54018) and ARC Centre for Advanced Manufacturing of Prefabricated Housing (IC150100023). Also, it was performed in part at the Materials Characterization and Fabrication Platform (MCFP) at the University of Melbourne and the Victorian Node of the Australian National Fabrication Facility (ANFF).

REFERENCES

- [1] K.T. Nguyen, P. Weerasinghe, P. Mendis, T. Ngo, J. Barnett, Performance of modern building façades in fire: a comprehensive review, *Electronic Journal of Structural Engineering* 16, 2016, pp. 69-86.
- [2] T.D. Ngo, Q.T. Nguyen, P. Tran, Heat release and flame propagation in prefabricated modular unit with GFRP composite facades, *Building Simulation*, Springer, 2016, pp. 607-616.
- [3] P. Hayes, How Lacrosse and Grenfell have dramatically altered the litigation and regulatory landscape, *Journal of Building Survey, Appraisal & Valuation* 7(1), 2018, pp. 48-60.
- [4] J. Anderson, L. Boström, R. Jansson McNamee, Fire Safety of Façades, 2017.
- [5] Q. Nguyen, P. Mendis, T. Ngo, C. Nguyen, D. Bhattacharyya, Effects of nanoclay on fire performance of hybrid nano composites, *The 19th International Conference on Composite Materials*.
- [6] A.R. Bahramian, Pyrolysis and flammability properties of novolac/graphite nanocomposites, *Fire Safety Journal*, 61, 2013, pp. 265-273.
- [7] M.Á. Cárdenas, D. García-López, A. García-Vilchez, J.F. Fernández, J.C. Merino, J.M. Pastor, Synergy between organo-bentonite and nanofillers for polymer based fire retardant applications, *Applied Clay Science*, 45(3), 2009, pp. 139-146.
- [8] H.G. Dodiuk, Sidney H., *Handbook of thermoset plastics*, Elsevier, 2014.
- [9] Ü.B. Alkan, N. Kızılcan, In situ preparation of resol/sepiolite nanocomposites, *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 195, 2015, pp. 2067-2075.
- [10] N. Kızılcan, G. Özkaraman, In situ preparation of resol/clay nanocomposites, *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, 129(5), 2013, pp. 2966-2976.
- [11] M. López, M. Blanco, M. Martín, I. Mondragon, Influence of cure conditions on properties of resol/layered silicate nanocomposites, *Polymer Engineering & Science*, 52(6), 2012, pp. 1161-1172.
- [12] T. NGUYEN, Fire performance of GFRP facade systems, 2015.
- [13] G. Tartaglione, D. Tabuani, G. Camino, Thermal and morphological characterisation of organically modified sepiolite, *Microporous and Mesoporous Materials*, 107(1-2), 2008, pp. 161-168.
- [14] Y. Liu, J. Zhao, C.-L. Deng, L. Chen, D.-Y. Wang, Y.-Z. Wang, Flame-retardant effect of sepiolite on an intumescent flame-retardant polypropylene system, *Industrial & Engineering Chemistry Research*, 50(4), 2011, pp. 2047-2054.
- [15] N.A. Mohd Zaini, H. Ismail, A. Rusli, Short Review on Sepiolite-Filled Polymer Nanocomposites, *Polymer-Plastics Technology and Engineering*, 56(15), 2017, pp. 1665-1679.
- [16] A. Zotti, A. Borriello, A. Martone, V. Antonucci, M. Giordano, M. Zarrelli, Effect of sepiolite filler on mechanical behaviour of a bisphenol A-based epoxy system, *Composites Part B: Engineering*, 67, 2014, pp. 400-409.
- [17] E. Palacios, P. Leret, M.J. De La Mata, J.F. Fernández, A.H. De Aza, M.A. Rodríguez, F. Rubio-Marcos, Self-Forming 3D Core-Shell Ceramic Nanostructures for Halogen-Free Flame Retardant Materials, *ACS applied materials & interfaces*, 8(14), 2016, pp. 9462-9471.
- [18] C. Kaynak, C.C. Tasan, Effects of production parameters on the structure of resol type phenolic resin/layered silicate nanocomposites, *European polymer journal*, 42(8), 2006, pp. 1908-1921.

[19] J.-C. Munoz, H. Ku, F. Cardona, D. Rogers, Effects of catalysts and post-curing conditions in the polymer network of epoxy and phenolic resins: Preliminary results, *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*, 202(1-3), 2008, pp. 486-492.